

CHROMATO-MASS-SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF THE SYNTHESIZED SUBSTANCES

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Annotation. The composition of the raw materials used in the synthesis of acetaldehyde, the catalyst CCF (cadmium calcium phosphate), was analyzed and determined. Based on the analysis results, active cadmium oxide was isolated from the KKF catalyst and new catalysts were prepared. Acetaldehyde and acetone were synthesized from the prepared catalysts.

The qualitative and quantitative properties of the synthesized substances were analyzed and confirmed by chromatography-mass spectrometry methods.

Keywords: Acetylene, water, acetaldehyde, acetone, CCF (cadmium calcium phosphate), CaO, CdO, P₂O₅, MgO.

A mass spectrometer determines the mass and structure of a substance. This step works as follows:

Each molecule ionizes (loses or gains electrons).

Ions move through an electric/magnetic field.

The device determines the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of ions.

The result is a mass spectrum - a graph showing the intensity and mass of each ion.

In this method, each substance separated by chromatography is sequentially sent to a mass spectrometer where it is detected. These two stages are connected sequentially in one system.

Pharmaceutical - in the determination of pure or mixtures of medicinal products,

criminalistics - in the detection of narcotic drugs or poisons,

ecology - determination of pollutants in air, water, soil,

food industry - used to detect preservatives or pesticides in food.

The obtained spectra were identified using the i-NIST standard library. The composition of the studied sample was calculated based on TIC (Total Ion Chromatogram) - total ion chromatogram data.

MS-NW-9104
acetaldehyde
 C_2H_4O

(Mass of molecular ion: 44)

Figure 1. Chromato-mass spectrum of acetaldehyde

MS-IW-7880
acetone
 C_3H_6O

(Mass of molecular ion: 58)

Figure 2. Chromato-mass spectrum of acetone

The mass spectrum of acetaldehyde (Fig. 1) is characterized by the following main peaks:

- ~29 -100% (main peak) $[CHO]^+$ fragment - most stable and widespread;
- ~44 - average peak, molecular ion $[C_2H_4O]^+$ - ionic form of the entire molecule;

~43 - upper peak $[\text{CH}_3\text{CO}]^+$ - simple fragment, often found in ketones and aldehydes;

~15 - Low $[\text{CH}_3]^+$ - methyl group fragment.

The strongest peak in this spectrum is at $m/z = 29$, representing the $[\text{CHO}]^+$ fragment of the acetaldehyde molecule.

At the same time, the molecular ion peak at $m/z = 44$ confirms the total mass of the substance.

The mass spectrum of acetone (Fig. 2) is characterized by the following main peaks:

~43 - 100% (main peak) $[\text{CH}_3\text{CO}]^+$ - this fragment is very characteristic of ketones;

~58 - approximately 80%, molecular ion $[\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}]^+$ - whole acetone molecule;

~15 - low $[\text{CH}_3]^+$ - methyl fragment;

~29 - less intense $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$ - ethyl fragment.

The peak at $m/z = 58$ indicates the molecular ion of acetone.

$m/z = 43$ is the main fragment, which is the most intense and stable $[\text{CH}_3\text{CO}]^+$ ion in the spectrum.

Chromatography-mass spectrometry is a highly accurate, cost-effective, and versatile technology for chemical analysis. It is one of the most reliable tools in chemistry for structural, qualitative, and quantitative analysis of substances.

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